

The occurrence of the Republic of Moldova as a topic in the Romanian presidential elections of 2024-2025

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Abstract

The Romanian presidential elections of 2024-2025 marked a turning point in the country's post-communist political trajectory, given their annulment and rerun as well as the ideological polarization they revealed. Central to the electoral discourse was the Republic of Moldova, whose EU candidacy and strategic relevance were instrumentalized by candidates across the political spectrum. This article explores how Moldova emerged as a theme in Romanian political messaging, while examining the interplay between historical sentiment, identity politics, and foreign policy narratives. Through a discourse analysis of campaign materials, speeches, and electoral data, the study tests three hypotheses: that Moldova's EU trajectory shaped pro-European messaging; that nationalist candidates used Moldova as a symbolic issue to mobilize support; and that Moldovan citizens with Romanian dual citizenship significantly influenced the electoral outcome. The findings confirm that Moldova was framed either as a strategic partner or a nationalist cause, depending on ideological orientation. Candidates such as Nicușor Dan emphasized pragmatic cooperation and democratic resilience, while George Simion and other nationalists invoked themes of reunification and cultural erasure. The article also highlights Romania's concrete contributions to Moldova's EU integration, including financial aid, infrastructure projects, and diplomatic support. Ultimately, the study reveals Moldova's dual role as both a foreign policy concern and a domestic electoral tool, reflecting tensions in Romania's regional positioning amid rising populism and hybrid threats.

Keywords

Romanian presidential elections; Republic of Moldova; nationalist discourse; EU enlargement; democratic resilience

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Introduction

The Romanian presidential elections of 2024-2025 marked an unprecedented moment in the country's post-communist political history, not only due to their annulment and rerun but also because of the divisions it revealed and deepened within society. Such differences were emphasized by some of the prominent topics that helped the candidates shape their political messages, not the least of which revolved around the Republic of Moldova and its future in relation to Romania and to its own EU integration bid. This article investigates the instrumentalization of Moldova within Romanian political discourse amid the 2024-2025 presidential campaigns, and seeks to understand how historical, cultural, and strategic narratives were mobilized by candidates across the ideological spectrum.

The central research question guiding this study is: How and why did the Republic of Moldova become a significant theme in the Romanian presidential elections of 2024-2025, and what does this reveal about the evolving nature of antagonistic nationalist and pro-European political messaging in Romania? Subsidiary questions include: To what extent did Moldova's EU trajectory influence Romanian electoral narratives? How did different political actors frame Moldova in relation to Romania's strategic interests and identity politics?

To guide the analysis of Moldova's role in the Romanian presidential elections of 2024-2025, this study proposes three interrelated hypotheses. First, it is hypothesized that Moldova's recent EU candidacy and constitutional referendum significantly influenced the framing of political messages among pro-European candidates, who highlighted the values of strategic partnership and regional stability. Second, nationalist and populist candidates are expected to have instrumentalized Moldova as a symbolic and emotional issue, using it to mobilize identity-based support and challenge mainstream narratives, particularly through calls for reunification and more or less overt anti-EU rhetoric. Third, the presence of Moldovan citizens with Romanian dual citizenship is hypothesized to have had a sizeable impact on the electoral outcome, especially in favor of candidates promoting Moldova's European integration, as evidenced by voting patterns and turnout data.

These hypotheses will be tested through a discourse analysis of campaign materials, speeches, and electoral data, contextualized within Romania's broader geopolitical and institutional landscape. Official campaign and party websites will be corroborated with messages emitted at various points during the pre-election period, to observe coherence and inconsistencies, within a predominantly comparative endeavor. In support of this qualitative approach, the literature will also be reviewed, albeit the recent nature of the topic at hand means that a rather shallow body thereof has become available to date. Consequently, we will use reputable media sources to select recent quotes from the political messages of the candidates, some of which have already been translated into English. Finally, occasional quantitative elements will be included, chiefly from the official websites of the electoral bodies of Romania and Moldova.

The present research contributes to the literature in several ways. Theoretically, it bridges the gap between electoral studies and foreign policy analysis by examining how external relations - particularly with Moldova - are internalized within national political campaigns. Methodologically, it employs a content and discourse analysis of political programs, speeches, and campaign materials, contextualized within Romania's broader geopolitical positioning and EU commitments. The study also draws on comparative insights from Romanian political parties and their ideological precepts, offering an understanding of how Moldova's symbolic and strategic relevance is refracted through Romania's domestic political lens.

The article is structured as follows: The first section reviews the existing literature on Romanian-Moldovan relations and Moldova's EU candidacy. The second section explores the historical

and strategic significance of Moldova in Romanian political discourse. The third section examines Romania's concrete contributions to Moldova's EU integration to reflect the breadth of the pragmatic stakes encountered within this dossier. The fourth section gauges the occurrence of Moldova in the programs of Romanian political parties. The fifth section explains the peculiarities of the Romanian presidential elections of 2024-2025. The sixth section analyses how Moldova was framed by different candidates during the 2024-2025 elections. The final section discusses the implications of these findings for Romania's democratic trajectory and regional role, particularly in the context of rising populism and hybrid threats.

Literature review

The literature focusing on Romanian-Moldovan relations is ample and includes works of historiography, culture and language, albeit our interest chiefly lies in the common EU path pursued by the two countries most notably after the momentous decision to grant the Republic of Moldova its EU candidate status, in June 2022. Romania's special relationship with its eastern neighbor has largely shaped its actions regarding the promotion of the EU's enlargement policy. As shown by Toderas (2024), Romania's efforts to advance its national interests within the broader framework of EU enlargement come with particular emphasis on its support for the Republic of Moldova's accession. The pre-accession bid of the country is also the subject of various articles, such as Gherasim's (2025) ample study of the resilience of the Moldovan civil society amid what are bound to be protracted negotiations, or Pop-Flanja's (2024) analysis on Romania's involvement in combating disinformation and consolidating democratic resilience in Moldova, as part of its EU integration trajectory, as well as Pop-Flanja and Herța's study on the interplay between OSCE and local NGOs in the process of conflict transformation in Moldova. There is also a noticeable tendency to exhibit similarities between this dossier and those of East-Central EU members whose negotiations occurred in the late-1990s and early-2000s, owing to the past context defined by communism as well as to the cultural closeness especially with Romania, which has been a member state for almost two decades. As such, Ursu et al. (2024) see an opportunity in "learning" from the experience of the most recent members of the EU, given the likelihood of candidates stumbling over the same core of the *acquis*, a viewpoint that we share, so long as it fosters mutual exchange and does not place the recipient country in a demeaning position. Because of the onset of war in Ukraine, the literature also dwells upon the joint prospects of Chișinău and Kyiv as aspiring EU members. Thus, in Emerson et al. (2023), the case is made for this type of pairing, which has worked before, and the arguments are drawn from the reports made available by the EU Commission and more.

An attempt at liaising the topic of Moldova with the political programs of three candidates in the first round of the Romanian presidential election of 2024 was made by Mureșan (2024), but none of the three case studies corresponds to the winner of the final round, or to the candidates that proceeded to it, and the analysis is an *ex-ante* one, thus it does not connect the topic to the outcome of the election or to the controversy that followed.

While our research is compatible with the views exhibited by such articles, the originality thereof stems from the fact that there is a need to cover the liaison between Moldova's new-found EU path, Romania's willingness to commit to the speeding-up of the enlargement policy including for Ukraine, and the transposition of such topics into the electoral programs that shape national strategic views in this regard.

The Romanian presidential elections of 2024-2025 were unexpectedly sinuous and, albeit they already occur in the literature from the juridical angle owing to the decision of the Constitutional Court

to cancel the first round, like in Mercescu (2025), it is our view that an analysis of the political messages that defined the process is needed. Pantea (2024) already broached the rise of populist parties in the Romanian electoral realm and comprehensively explained the sovereigntist label so swiftly and shallowly adopted by them. Mariș (2025) tackled the subject by attempting to gauge the resilience of Romanian democracy in the light of the cancellation of the presidential election. However, the literature stops short of connecting this ample topic to one of the roots that fed into the essence of nationalist discourse in Romania, namely the special case of the Republic of Moldova. Hence, our positioning stems from the analysis of the occurrence of this topic in the political programs of the main candidates, in keeping with the doctrines of the parties that stood beside them, to reveal how the immense cleavage opened up in society manifested itself in the creation of this segment of the electoral message. This will enable one to better comprehend the instrumentalization of sensitive historical and cultural topics, woven into the fabric of Romania's EU and NATO commitments, while commenting on the different styles politicians embrace when dealing with such matters, from walking on eggshells to stampeding and stirring the murky waters as much as possible.

Why is the Republic of Moldova meaningful to the Romanian political stage?

The Republic of Moldova occupies a distinctive position within Romania's political discourse, shaped by historical, cultural, and strategic factors that continue to influence bilateral relations, whilst carrying a certain weight from an electoral standpoint. The shared linguistic and ethnic heritage between the two countries, rooted in their common history prior to the Soviet annexation of Bessarabia in 1940, has fostered a sense of kinship that transcends conventional diplomacy and often kindles emotional responses to events on both sides of the border. This connection is often raised by Romanian political actors to justify sustained engagement with Moldova, both in terms of cultural support and geopolitical strategy, albeit the nationalist element may also be encountered whenever such topics are invoked.

Romania's interest in Moldova is far from being merely symbolic, as it is in the former's best geopolitical interest to secure a West-leaning path for both Moldova and Ukraine, countries which, unlike Romania, have a history of pendulation between Russia's sphere of influence and the EU (Corpădean, 2024). As a member of the EU and NATO, Romania sees Moldova as a buffer zone between the Euro-Atlantic community and Russia's assertive ambitions, most notably after the invasion of Crimea from 2014. Moreover, the unresolved conflict in Transnistria, where Russian troops remain stationed as a thorn in the back to Romania's interests, underscores the fragility of Moldova's neutrality and very sovereignty, as well as the importance of its alignment with Western institutions. The war triggered by Russia against Ukraine has amplified such apprehensions and prompted unprecedented closeness between the EU and Moldova, as part of the latter's application for full membership. Consequently, Romania has positioned itself as a staunch advocate for Moldova's European integration, offering technical assistance, financial aid, and diplomatic backing in Brussels (Toderaș, 2024). Bucharest's own sinuous experience during accession negotiations is likely to serve as a useful case study for Moldova, as long as its rather fragile leadership remains committed to EU integration (Corpădean and Oprescu, 2023).

Despite the visible commitment to the aforementioned endeavor exhibited by both sides, the political relationship between Romania and Moldova is complicated by internal dynamics. In Moldova, the oscillation between pro-European and pro-Russian political actions has created a volatile environment that challenges the EU's efforts to promote reform and democratic consolidation, as it became noticeable in the case of the 2024 presidential election (Mihailov et al., 2025). This volatility is

further exacerbated by pro-Russian political parties that use propaganda and disinformation to manipulate public perception and sow fear and confusion (Nistor, 2024). Meanwhile, in Romania, political parties often leverage the Moldovan issue for domestic gain, appealing to nationalist sentiments and the idea of reunification, often with unclear ties to the Kremlin's divisive and downright hostile intentions in the region. While the notion of unification remains a contentious albeit largely symbolic issue, it continues to shape public discourse, stir complicated feelings and influence Romania's approach to this Eastern neighbor.

Despite these complexities, Romania's engagement with Moldova has reflected a long-term vision of closeness and cultural continuity since September 1991, when Bucharest became the first capital to recognize the independence of the former Soviet Republic. The bilateral relationship, upgraded in 2010 to the level of a strategic partnership, is marked by more than frequent diplomatic exchanges, as it has encompassed joint government meetings, infrastructure projects and educational initiatives, many of which are furthered due to Romania's EU membership (Corpădean, 2016; Albu Comănescu, 2022). From enhancing Chișinău's energy sustainability and independence of Russian resources to safeguarding the position of the Romanian language, Bucharest has opted for pragmatic action despite the proclivity of local politicians for the emotional card when broaching such topics. Moreover, civil societies in Romania and the Moldova have evolved in close connection to the willingness to develop a strong democratic environment (Grad-Rusu and Grad, 2025). However, this closeness also presents challenges on the Moldovan side, as segments of society, particularly the Russian-speaking minority, view Romania's involvement with suspicion, fearing a loss of sovereignty or cultural erasure. This became apparent once again during the 2024 presidential election, and the EU referendum that was attached to it, when 95% of the residents of the autonomous region of Găgăuzia cast a ballot against this national priority, while in the breakaway region of Transnistria, the trend was also towards a no vote, with 69% (CEC, 2024).

What has Romania done to facilitate the integration of the Republic of Moldova into the EU?

The extent to which Moldova can be coherently used as an electoral topic in Romania at present depends on the concrete nature of the interactions between the two, to gauge the realities that could permeate the political discourse. Furthermore, the fact that one million Moldovans also hold the Romanian citizenship (including President Maia Sandu) is indicative of a sizeable electoral corps, not to be taken for granted by any aspiring politician at this time (Digi24, 2024).

One of Romania's most tangible contributions to bilateral ties has been its role in securing and channeling EU funding to Moldova, together with the know-how needed to create a project management culture in the EU candidate state. Through programs such as Interreg NEXT Romania-Moldova 2021-2027, Moldova has gained access to over €97 million in non-reimbursable financial assistance for joint projects in health, education, tourism, climate resilience, and border management (Interreg Next, 2024). Romania has also facilitated Moldova's participation in broader EU initiatives, such as the Connecting Europe Facility, which allocated €3.5 million to modernize rail infrastructure between Iași and Ungheni, a critical step toward integrating Moldova into the EU's transport network (Moldpres, 2025). These investments not only carry tangible gains for Moldova's infrastructure and institutional capacity but also signal its readiness to meet EU standards and manage pre-accession resources.

Beyond funding, Romania has played an active role in keeping Moldova on a pro-European trajectory, especially during politically volatile periods. Romanian leaders have consistently voiced support for Moldova's European path in Brussels and other international forums, emphasizing the

importance of democratic reform and regional security, topics with which Romania itself had experienced hurdles on its EU-bound path. This support has been particularly visible in countering Russia-orchestrated hybrid threats, including disinformation campaigns and political interference, which seek to derail Moldova's EU bid. Romanian officials have also been among the ones to pledge technical assistance in areas such as judicial reform, anti-corruption, and public administration, sectors that are central to EU accession criteria and form the core *acquis*, centered around chapters 23 and 24, known to be the thorniest for EU negotiations (MFA MD, 2024).

The personal relationship between the Romanian and Moldovan leadership has always been a decisive factor in gauging bilateral relations, ranging from downright hostility during the Dodon regime to openness and mutual support once Maia Sandu took over. Indeed, Presidents Maia Sandu and Nicușor Dan have followed in the footsteps of the previous Romanian administration and exhibit a close and cooperative rapport, marked by frequent meetings and joint public appearances, including to bolster their political capital. This partnership serves as a useful example for our research, enabling us to see the impact of Romanian-Moldovan ties on the highest-ranking political offices within the two countries. For instance, during official visits and informal events, such as the Wolves Festival in Orheiul Vechi, the two leaders have emphasized unity, democratic resilience, and cultural continuity, appearing to carefully adopt an EU-centered terminology. Maia Sandu has repeatedly praised Romania's unwavering support, describing it as essential to Moldova's survival as a sovereign, democratic state free from external coercion, which is a very charged message to utter in a decisive election year for her country (Romanian Presidency, 2025). The parliamentary ballot on 28 September 2005 is rightly seen as crucial to the pursuit of the EU course of the Republic and is likely to be set against the background of Russian hybrid interference, a subject that Romania is no stranger to after the latest presidential election.

Romania's engagement with Moldova under Maia Sandu's leadership has also extended to strategic coordination on regional security, with both countries aligning their positions on Russia's war in Ukraine and recognizing its implications for Moldova's sovereignty and European aspirations. Romania's support for Ukraine is understood as indirectly bolstering Moldova's own security, whilst the support Bucharest has pledged to Kiyv's EU application positions Romania as a promoter of the embattled enlargement policy that Moldova is due to benefit from.

Moldova as a political subject for Romanian parties

The findings above show that for Romania, the political impact of the very act of tackling Moldova is paramount, and that the subject itself is unavoidable, if only due to the size of the population holding the dual citizenship. In what follows we examine how the leading political parties have adapted their discourse to the current state of bilateral relations, as a prerequisite for the analysis of the electoral approach to the matter during the presidential vote of 2024-2025. From the onset it is to be underlined that while most parties invoke Moldova in the context of European integration and regional cooperation, others, most notably the Alliance for the Union of Romanians (AUR), employ it as a nationalist rallying cry rooted in historical revisionism and identity politics. In a country where 56% of the population trusts the EU and 70% considers that their country has profited from joining the Union, promoting an openly anti-EU agenda is still a political gamble, despite the Eurosceptic regional voices and the empowerment thereof from the Trump 2 administration (Eurobarometer, 2025).

The Social Democratic Party (PSD), Romania's largest traditional party post-1989, generally approaches Moldova through the lens of pragmatic diplomacy and cultural affinity. PSD has supported Moldova's European path, in synergy with the Party of European Socialists that it is affiliated with, and

has made a point of maintaining institutional cooperation, but it avoids overt nationalist rhetoric (PSD, 2022). Moldova is often referenced in PSD's foreign policy agenda as a partner in regional development and EU alignment, rather than as a subject of irredentist ambition, which is indicative of the "thread lightly" current.

The National Liberal Party (PNL), historically more center-right, also supports Moldova's EU integration endeavor and Maia Sandu personally, and has emphasized infrastructure cooperation, mimicking a traditionally liberal economic rhetoric that is friendly towards the business milieu (Moldpres, 2024). PNL governments have facilitated cross-border projects and advocated for Moldova's interests in Brussels and within the EPP group, so it would be difficult to find episodes in which the party would have hampered Chișinău's European ambitions. Much like PSD, a party with which the liberals have found themselves in a government alliance since November 2021, PNL tends to frame Moldova as a strategic partner rather than a nationalist cause, aligning its discourse with EU norms and regional stability.

The Save Romania Union (USR), a progressive and reformist party, currently part of the broad pro-EU government, also focuses on Moldova primarily in terms of democratic consolidation and anti-corruption, in keeping with the most stringent requirements of the *acquis*. Like its coalition partners, USR supports Moldova's European aspirations and has collaborated with Moldovan civil society but stops short of engaging in nationalist narratives. Instead, its emphasis lies on institutional reform and the rule of law, in a likely attempt to portray consistency with the platform of modernization and transparency it has advocated at national level (USR, 2025).

In stark contrast to the aforementioned political entities, the Alliance for the Union of Romanians (AUR) has made Moldova a centerpiece of its nationalist agenda. Founded in 2019 and rising rapidly in popularity, AUR promotes the idea of reunification between Romania and Moldova, framing it as a historical imperative and moral duty. As such, the party draws on the legacy of Greater Romania and the 1918 union of Bessarabia with Romania, portraying current borders as unjust remnants of Soviet aggression (AUR, 2025). What is of utmost interest is that AUR leaders have repeatedly questioned the legitimacy of the Moldovan government, particularly under President Maia Sandu and the pro-European Party of Action and Solidarity (PAS), with the Alliance's rhetoric toward Moldova growing increasingly aggressive, especially in the lead-up to Moldova's 2025 parliamentary elections (Adevărul, 2025). George Simion, the leader of AUR, has been banned from entering Moldova until at least 1 October 2028, following a series of incidents deemed threatening to national security and public order. The ban, originally imposed in 2018 after Simion's actions during a unionist demonstration considered to be provocative, was reaffirmed after his repeated attempts to enter the country and his inflammatory rhetoric targeting Moldovan authorities (Newsweek, 2024). Simion has accused President Maia Sandu's government of corruption and illegitimacy, framing his exclusion as politically motivated and part of a broader campaign against Romanian-Moldovan unity. Moldovan officials, however, maintain that the decision is a legal measure to protect the country's democratic institutions from destabilizing influences, especially amid growing concerns over disinformation networks linked to AUR and its affiliates (Moldova1, 2025).

AUR's rhetoric towards Moldova is often emotionally charged, invoking themes of betrayal, cultural erasure, and national rebirth, while such discourse is tied to its broader anti-globalist and anti-EU stance. While AUR nominally supports Moldova's European integration (AUR, 2024), it often frames the EU as a threat to national sovereignty and cultural identity, in what appears to be a paradoxical position meant for AUR to appeal to both pro-unification voters and Eurosceptics, whilst consolidating its base among those disillusioned with mainstream politics.

Drawing from the above, it becomes apparent that Moldova remains a relevant subject for Romanian political parties, but its role differs sharply depending on ideological orientation. PSD, PNL, and USR treat Moldova as a strategic partner in European integration, emphasizing cooperation and development, whereas AUR instrumentalizes the neighboring country as a nationalist symbol, advocating for reunification and challenging the legitimacy of current borders. This divergence was bound to be reflected by the messages conceived by the presidential candidates in the complicated election of 2024-2025, as we will show below.

The Romanian presidential elections of 2024-2025: an unprecedented endeavor

To comprehend how the Republic of Moldova permeated the electoral message during the Romanian presidential elections of 2024–2025, it is first and foremost necessary to explain what has made this ballot stand out, as an unprecedented political and constitutional episode in the country's post-communist history. Initially scheduled for November and December 2024, the elections were annulled by the Constitutional Court on 6 December, merely two days before the second round and with ballots already being cast abroad, following revelations of foreign interference, undeclared campaign financing, and digital manipulation. This decision plunged Romania into a constitutional crisis, prompted ample international attention (taking the form of both support and criticism – for more details, see, in this issue, Mișcoiu and Naumescu, 2025), triggered some internal protests, and led to the formation of an emergency government tasked with restoring electoral integrity and public trust.

At the heart of the controversy was the unexpected first-round victory of independent candidate Călin Georgescu, a far-right populist whose campaign was marked by peculiar messages and media strategies, mysticism, nationalism, pro-Russian rhetoric, and an aggressive digital media drive. Georgescu's rise was largely attributed to his dominance on TikTok, where his account reportedly amassed over 298.000 followers and 3.8 million likes, enabling him to fly under the radar of the political mainstream (Politico, 2024; Tavalla and Matiuța, 2025). Romanian intelligence services and the Supreme Council of National Defense (CSAT) later declassified reports indicating that Georgescu's campaign had benefited from coordinated disinformation efforts, cyberattacks on electoral infrastructure, and illicit foreign funding, allegedly linked to Russian interests (Administrația Prezidențială, 2024). As a consequence, the Constitutional Court cited these findings, along with Georgescu's failure to declare any campaign expenditures despite evidence of such promotional activity, as grounds for annulling the election (Mercescu, 2025).

The annulment ignited protests across Romania, with thousands of demonstrators, some pro-Georgescu and others pro-European, taking to the streets of Bucharest and other major cities, in a clear indication of profound societal divisions. The political fallout was swift and led to the resignation of PM Marcel Ciolacu, followed by that of President Klaus Iohannis, in February 2025, following an attempted impeachment. The interim presidency was assumed by Senate President Ilie Bolojan, who oversaw the transition to a new electoral cycle scheduled for May 2025.

The rerun elections were no less dramatic, with Călin Georgescu barred from candidacy (Biroul Electoral Central, 2025) due to ongoing criminal investigations (including charges of incitement against the constitutional order and support for fascist groups) and his political mantle being taken up by George Simion, leader of AUR. Already a polarizing figure, George Simion intensified his nationalist rhetoric and positioned himself as the voice of disenfranchised Romanians, a strategy which enabled him to win the first round with 40.96% of the vote, ahead of Bucharest Mayor Nicușor Dan, who secured 20.99%. The second round, held on 18 May 2025, was framed as a referendum on Romania's

democratic future, where Nicușor Dan, running as an independent with pro-European credentials and a reputation for institutional reform, ultimately prevailed with 53.6% of the vote (ROAEP, 2025).

When analyzing the type of political messages uttered during the 2024-2025 electoral cycle, one has to bear in mind several particularities of this period, of which we will emphasize the adoption of populist trends and topics that had worked wonders closer to Romania, namely in Hungary, Poland and Slovakia, or even the artificial donning of the MAGA cap that several candidates had attempted (some literally). In a country that has benefitted enormously from EU integration and has shown constant support for and commitment to its NATO obligations, whilst constantly exhibiting distrust in Russia's regional actions, the manipulatory exploitation of such topics was unexpected. The same holds true of the power of digital platforms in shaping political outcomes, with TikTok, in particular, being accused of algorithmic bias and failing to curb coordinated inauthentic behavior (Global Witness, 2025). Romanian regulators and the European Commission launched what can only be deemed as belated investigations under the Digital Services Act, scrutinizing the platform's role in amplifying extremist content and foreign-sponsored narratives (European Commission, 2024). In fact, the generally delayed action by Romanian institutions also exhibited the poor preparedness for such disruptions and underscored the need for genuine digital governance and electoral safeguards in what ought to have been acknowledged as an already ongoing time of hybrid threats.

Moldova in the political programs of the main candidates

It is under such auspices that the Romanian presidential elections of 2024-2025 accommodated the subject of the Republic of Moldova, emerging as a leitmotif in the political programs of the main candidates, amid a rather peculiar interplay of historical sentiment, strategic interests, and ideological positioning. Moldova's symbolic and geopolitical significance was once again interpreted differently across the political spectrum, with candidates ranging from independent reformers to nationalist populists offering divergent visions for Romania's relationship with its eastern neighbor. The echoes of this preoccupation for Moldova were felt in the mobilization of the Moldovan electorate with dual citizenship, which mirrored the decisive pro-European vote already cast by the Moldovan diaspora in the national presidential election and referendum. In the decisive round of the Romanian presidential ballot, a record turnout in Moldova proper, with 138.320 votes cast, 88% going towards Nicușor Dan (ROAEP, 2025), is indicative of a considerable trend among the Moldovans that hold the Romanian citizenship, to be scrutinized in future elections as well.

In the following paragraphs it is our intent to dissect the approach to Moldova of the most important presidential candidates, follow the consistency with the guidelines of the political parties they belonged to or were supported by, and attempt to connect such views with the changes occurring in the Romanian political life.

Nicușor Dan, the eventual winner and an independent candidate with a technocratic and pro-European profile, adopted a pragmatic approach to Moldova. His program (Nicușor Dan, 2025) emphasized Romania's role as a strategic partner in Moldova's European integration bid, particularly in the wake of Moldova's 2024 constitutional referendum that enshrined EU membership as a national goal. Moreover, Nicușor Dan pledged to deepen bilateral cooperation in infrastructure, energy, and education, and to support Moldova's efforts to combat Russian disinformation and hybrid threats, which was in keeping with his stance at national level, in the light of the election interference allegations. He avoided nationalist rhetoric and instead framed Moldova as a sovereign partner whose success was vital to regional stability, in a skillful move meant to counter the disturbance caused in this respect by the far-right.

“This is a historic moment for both countries. Romania can become a regional leader, and the Republic of Moldova can become a trusted member of the European family. Only together, through clear projects and political will, can we succeed in putting this vision into practice” - Campaign speech, March 2025

The validation of this strategy came through the vote Nicușor Dan’s campaign received from Moldovans with Romanian citizenship even in the first round, with over 52% of them voting for him, a value that stood to grow in the decisive round. After his victory, Nicușor Dan publicly thanked on his Facebook account Moldovan citizens and President Maia Sandu, who had pledged her support openly for the pro-EU candidate, thus reaffirming his commitment to a shared European path and steering clear of any Romania-Moldova union controversy.

At the diametrically opposed end stood George Simion, leader of the AUR party, who did not hesitate to place Moldova at the center of his nationalist platform, holding true to his past preoccupations. A long-time unionist activist, George Simion’s program called for the outright reunification of Romania and Moldova, portraying the current borders as illegitimate and the Moldovan state as a historical anomaly. He proposed the enactment of constitutional reforms to facilitate unification and demanded the lifting of his entry ban into Moldova, which had been extended in February 2024 due to concerns over national security. George Simion’s rhetoric was confrontational, accusing Moldovan authorities of suppressing Romanian identity and suggesting that Romania would not intervene militarily in the event of a Russian attack on Moldova - indeed, a risky move that predictably drew widespread criticism.

“I am a unionist. I have always been a unionist; I was president of Action 2012. Basically, peacefully, democratically, through the will of both parties, we advocate for the union of the two Romanian states that exist today, and therefore for the abolition of the Republic of Moldova, which is, in fact, a Stalinist creation. I cannot stand and will never come to terms with this concept of Moldovan statism. I have fought against it. (...) I hate this artificial state called the Republic of Moldova, I have said so countless times.” - Presidential debate, February 2025

If one couples this with George Simion’s reluctant attitude towards Ukraine, there emerge the seeds of a controversial style of positioning Romania at the level of the region, at odds with the views exhibited by the other frontrunners.

To continue down the nationalist path, one should take into account the message of candidate Diana Șoșoacă, leader of the S.O.S. Romania party, whose approach tended to echo George Simion’s nationalist stance, but with even more radical overtones. Her program called for immediate reunification and the dissolution of Moldova’s sovereignty, framing the issue as a moral and historical imperative. Diana Șoșoacă also promoted peculiar theories about Western influence in Moldova and accused the EU of undermining Romanian identity, amid a campaign that was marked by inflammatory language and legal challenges, including investigations into hate speech and incitement.

“Maia Sandu is a traitor. She betrayed Moldovans, our brothers across the Prut River. I even wrote to her about it; she knows my opinion of her and her actions. She effectively sold out the Republic of Moldova and Moldovans. It’s a huge scandal there. I don’t need to tell you that she is supported by George Soros’s clan and that she has made a mockery of the citizens of the country she is supposed to represent.” - podcast appearance in October 2024

The aforementioned camp includes first-round winner Călin Georgescu, who depicted Moldova through a sovereigntist and anti-Western lens, while stopping short of advocating for outright unification and admitting to the existence of a Moldovan people. His program, on several occasions, rejected EU and NATO integration for both Romania and Moldova, advocating instead for a neutral

foreign policy and closer ties with Russia, for whose leader the candidate manifested an unusual dose of admiration.

“I have seen the results of the referendum: 50% are in favor of Russia, 50% in favor of Romania. Therefore, it is not possible to discuss unification, as it does not make sense. We must be patient, and the most important thing is what I have advocated for Romania and automatically advocate for Moldova, which is to consistently support the domestic economy so that people are happy, have jobs, and understand that they live for their land, for their country. (...) I don't think this is a time when you can discuss this aspect of unification. If it had been 90 to 10 in favor (sic!), you could have brought up this topic, but that is not the case.” - interview with Natalia Morari in March 2025

Candidates from mainstream parties, such as Marcel Ciolacu (PSD) and Nicolae Ciucă (PNL), adopted more moderate and diplomatic positions, similar to Nicușor Dan and quite openly at odds with the nationalist trio. For instance, Marcel Ciolacu emphasized Moldova's European trajectory and pledged continued support for President Maia Sandu's reform agenda. He also highlighted the importance of countering Russian propaganda and strengthening Moldova's democratic institutions.

“(...) our shared history and brotherly relations are a powerful catalyst and guarantee that Romania will remain a constant supporter of the economic development, stability, and security of the Republic of Moldova.” - dialogue with Maia Sandu, March 2024

Nicolae Ciucă, similarly, praised Moldova's EU referendum results and called for intensified cooperation in security and development, two leitmotifs of his unsuccessful presidential bid. Like Marcel Ciolacu, he carefully avoided nationalist appeals and focused on institutional cooperation and the strategic partnership that lies at the core of bilateral ties, therefore reflecting PNL's commitment to EU enlargement and regional stability.

“For the eastern part of the continent, integration into the EU is the only guarantee of development and prosperity. I celebrate this momentous day for our brothers across the Prut River, my heart with them, wishing them prosperity and success on their European journey.” - speech on Independence Day the Republic of Moldova, August 2024.

Conclusion

Moldova's presence in the 2024-2025 Romanian presidential campaigns revealed deep ideological divides, although it would be presumptuous to elevate the topic to the zenith of the debates. For technocratic and centrist candidates, Moldova was portrayed quite prudently as a strategic partner in European integration. For nationalist and populist figures, it was shaped into a symbol of historical unity and a rallying point for identity politics. The contrasting visions offered by Nicușor Dan and George Simion underscored the broader tension between pragmatic diplomacy and nationalist mobilization, making Moldova not just a foreign policy issue but a litmus test for Romania's democratic direction.

The findings of this study validate all three proposed hypotheses. First, Moldova's EU candidacy and strategic relevance were clearly reflected in the political messaging of pro-European candidates such as Nicușor Dan, Marcel Ciolacu, and Nicolae Ciucă, who emphasized bilateral cooperation, democratic resilience, and regional stability, aligning their views with Romania's EU commitments. Second, nationalist and populist figures, notably including George Simion, Diana Șoșoacă, and Călin Georgescu, instrumentalized Moldova as a symbolic and emotional issue, invoking themes of historical unity, cultural erasure, and anti-Western sentiment to mobilize identity-based support and challenge mainstream narratives. Their rhetoric, often confrontational and revisionist, contrasted sharply with the diplomatic tone of centrist candidates. Third, the electoral impact of

Moldovan citizens with Romanian dual citizenship was both measurable and significant, with a record turnout and overwhelming support for Nicușor Dan, thus confirming that Moldova's European trajectory resonated with this electorate and influenced the final outcome.

References

- Adevărul. 2025. "George Simion, mesaj plin de frustrare la adresa Maiei Sandu...", June 10. Available at <https://adevarul.ro/politica/simion-mesaj-plin-de-frustrare-la-adresa-2449684.html>.
- Administrația Prezidențială. 2024. Comunicat de presă. Available at <https://www.presidency.ro/ro/media/comunicat-de-presa1733327193>.
- Albu Comănescu, Radu. 2022. "Diplomația căilor multiple: Track one, track two și track one-and-a-half diplomacy: Clarificări și adaptări conceptuale." In Ioan Bolovan and Melania Gabriela Ciot (eds.) *Românii și România în context european. Istorie și diplomație*, Editura Academiei.
- AUR. 2024. "AUR și-a prezentat, la Chișinău, candidații la alegerile europarlamentare din 9 iunie", April 21. Available at <https://partidulaur.ro/aur-si-a-prezentat-la-chisinau-candidatii>.
- AUR. 2025. "Programul Partidului Politic Alianța pentru Unirea Românilor" Available at <https://partidulaur.ro/program/>.
- Biroul Electoral Central. 2025. Decizie privind respingerea înregistrării candidaturii independente a domnului Georgescu Călin la alegerile pentru Președintele României din anul 2025. March 9. Available https://prezidentiale2025.bec.ro/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/decizie_18D.pdf.
- Comisia Electorală Centrală a Republicii Moldova. 2024. Referendum republican constituțional. Available at <https://pvt12024.cec.md/cec-template-referendum-results.html>.
- Corpădean, Adrian-Gabriel. 2016. "Assessing Romania's Strategic Partnerships - Recent Endeavours in Romanian-Moldavian Relations." *Der Donauraum, Zeitschrift des Institutes für den Donauraum und Mitteleuropa*, 56(1-2): 107-121.
- Corpădean, Adrian-Gabriel. 2024. "The shared patrimony of Romania and Ukraine in the shadow of Russia." In Adrian-Gabriel Corpădean and Laura Herța (eds.) *The War against Ukraine, Europeanization, and Impact on Cultural Heritage Narratives in the Candidate Countries*, Cluj-Napoca: Presa Universitară Clujeană.
- Corpădean, Adrian-Gabriel, and Mihaela Oprescu. 2023. "Comparative views on East-Central European member states' integration experience and the Western Balkans." In Adrian-Gabriel Corpădean (ed.) *A model of transference of the EU integration experience from East-Central Europe to the Western Balkans*, London: Lambert Academic Publishing.
- Digi24. 2024. "Maia Sandu: Un milion de cetățeni din R. Moldova au pașaport românesc. Acest lucru trebuie să scurteze calea noastră spre UE", May 7. Available at <https://www.digi24.ro/stiri/un-milion-de-cetateni-din-moldova-au-pasaport-romanesec>.
- Emerson, Michael, Akhvlediani, Tinatin, Cenusă, Denis, Movchan, Veronika, and Artem Remizov. 2023. "The EU accession prospects of Ukraine, Moldova and Georgia." *CEPS In-depth analysis*, Brussels. Available at https://aprei.com.ua/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/CEPS-In-depth-analysis-2023-06_EU-Accession-Prospects-of-Ukraine-Moldova-and-Georgia.pdf.
- Eurobarometer. 2025. Standard EB 103, Spring. Available <https://europa.eu/eb/surveys/detail/3372>.

- European Commission. 2024. "Commission opens formal proceedings against TikTok on election risks under the Digital Services Act", December 14. Available at https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_24_6487.
- Gherasim, Gabriel. 2025. "The Republic of Moldova's civil society and democratic resilience in the context of the EU integration process." *Civil Szemle*, 22(1): 23-36. <http://doi.org/10.62560/csz.2025.01.2>.
- Global Witness. 2025. "TikTok algorithm continues to push multiple times more far-right content ...", May 15. Available at <https://globalwitness.org/en/campaigns/digital-threats/tiktok-algorithm-continues-to-push-multiple-times-more-far-right-content-to-users-ahead-of-romanian-election/>.
- Grad-Rusu, Elena, and Marius Grad. 2025. "Civil society and societal security. A comparative assessment between the Republic of Moldova and Romania in the current geopolitical context." *Civil Szemle*, 22(1): 125-138. <https://doi.org/10.62560/csz.2025.01.8>.
- Interreg Next. 2024. Evaluation Plan, Interreg VI-A NEXT Romania-Republic of Moldova Programme, Interreg VI-A NEXT Romania-Ukraine Programme. Available at https://ro-md.net/images/Evaluation_Plan_ROMDROUA_2021-2027_approved_MC.pdf
- Mariş, Daniela-Maria. 2025. "Four and a Half Elections; How the Super Election Year in Romania Was Extended." *Südosteuropa Mitteilungen*, 65: 9-23.
- Mercescu, Alexandra. 2025. "The Romanian Constitutional Court doing "militant democracy" (twice and more to come)." *Journal of Contemporary Central and Eastern Europe*, 33(1): 251-261. <https://doi.org/10.1080/25739638.2025.2482401>.
- Mihailov, Ana, DeSisto, Isabelle, Pop-Eleches, Grigore, Burmester, Isabell, and Ion Marandici. 2025. "Presidential Election and EU Referendum." *Moldovan Analytical Digest*, 1. Available at <https://be.research-collection.ethz.ch/server/api/core/bitstreams/f7844475-86b4-4a2a-aaaf-fad6af3aa16c>.
- Mişcoiu, Sergiu, and Valentin Naumescu. 2025. "Global perspectives and responses to Romania's 2024-2025 presidential elections." *Romanian Journal of Political Science*, 25(2): 13-28. <https://doi.org/10.528/zenodo.18480323>.
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs Republic of Moldova. 2024. Joint Statement by the Foreign Ministers of France, Germany, Romania and the Republic of Moldova. Chişinău, September 17. https://mfa.gov.md/sites/default/files/en_final_joint_statement_of_the_mpp_co-chairs.pdf.
- Moldova1. 2025. "Disinformation threatens Moldova's European path", July 31, <https://moldova1.md/p/54161>.
- Moldpres. 2024. "Romanian National Liberal Party, Moldova's Action and Solidarity Party to consolidate cooperation", November 11. <https://www.moldpres.md/eng/politics/romanian-national-liberal-party-moldovas-action-and-solidarity-party-to-consolidate-cooperation->.
- Moldpres. 2025. "Moldova to have first electrified railway: Iaşi – Ungheni line modernized with EU support", July 4. <https://www.moldpres.md/eng/economy/moldova-to-have-first-electrified-railway-iasi-ungheni-line-modernized-with-eu-support>.

- Mureșan, Antoanela Paula. 2024. "Coopération moldavo-roumaine dans les programmes politiques des candidats à la présidence roumaine de 2024." *Synergies Roumanie*, 19: 85-95. Available at <https://gerflint.fr/images/revues/Roumanie/Roumanie19/muresan.pdf>.
- Newsweek. 2024. "George Simion nu mai poate pune piciorul în Republica Moldova.", February 3. Available at <https://newsweek.ro/actualitate/george-simion-nu-mai-poate-pune-piciorul-in-republica-moldova-a-fost-interzis-pentru-inca-5-ani>.
- Nicușor Dan. 2025. "Viziunea România Onestă." Available at <https://nicusordan.ro/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Viziunea-Romania-Onesta.pdf>.
- Nistor, Roxana-Maria. 2024. "Shaping minds through discourse: Propaganda narratives in Moldova's 2024 elections." *Online Journal Modelling the New Europe*, 46: 190-210. <https://doi.org/10.24193/OJMNE.2024.46.09>.
- Pantea, Ana. 2024. "Sovereignist parties in Romania during the 2024 elections." *Studia Universitatis Babeș-Bolyai – Studia Europaea*, 69: 429-446.
- Politico. 2024. "Who is Călin Georgescu, the far-right TikTok star leading the Romanian election race?", November 25. <https://www.politico.eu/article/calın-georgescu-romania-elections/>.
- Pop-Flanja, Delia. 2024. "La résilience sociétale et la lutte contre la désinformation." *Synergies Roumanie*, 19: 53-68. Available at <https://gerflint.fr/revues/Roumanie/Roumanie19/pop.pdf>.
- Pop-Flanja, Delia, and Laura Herța. 2025. "Civil Society Actors and Conflict Management in Moldova. The role of OSCE and local NGOS." *Civil Szemle*, 22(1): 213-229. <https://doi.org/10.62560/csz.2025.01.13>.
- PSD. 2022. "Marcel Ciolacu: PSD va susține activ Republica Moldova pe tot parcursul procesului de integrare care va urma", March 3. Available at <https://www.psd.ro/marcel-ciolacu-psd-va-sustine-activ-republica-moldova-pe-tot-parcursul-procesului-de-integrare-care-va-urma/>.
- ROAEP. 2025. Alegeri prezidențiale. Available at <https://prezenta.roaep.ro/prezidentiale04052025/> and <https://prezenta.roaep.ro/prezidentiale18052025/>.
- Romanian Presidency. 2025. Conferința de presă comună a Președintelui României cu Președintele Republicii Moldova, Maia Sandu, June 10. Available at <https://www.presidency.ro/ro/media/declaratii-de-presa/conferinta-de-presa-comuna-a-presedintelui-romaniei-cu-presedintele-republicii-moldova-maia-sandu>.
- Tavalla, Reza, and Cristina Matiuța. 2025. "TikTok and the affective politics of digital populism: Nationalist youth mobilization in the 2024-2025 Romanian elections." *Romanian Journal of Political Science*, 25(1): 95-118. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18034781>.
- Toderaș, Nicolae. 2024. "Romania's Role in EU Enlargement: Challenges, Opportunities, and Strategic Preferences for the Republic of Moldova's Accession." *Europolity*, 18(2). Available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5061369>.
- Ursu, Viorica, Ursu, Daniel, and Maria Slobozianu. 2024. "Analysis of the experience of some EU Member States in the progress of accession to the EU." *Journal of Social Sciences*. 7(1): 171–187, [https://doi.org/10.52326/jss.utm.2024.7\(1\).14](https://doi.org/10.52326/jss.utm.2024.7(1).14).
- USR. 2025. "Republica Moldova." <https://usr.ro/program/republica-moldova/>.